

Research on the Application of Virtual Simulation Experiments in Medical Information Courses

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Abstract—Virtual simulation experiment, as a new teaching means and method, is widely used in the teaching of experimental courses in higher medical schools. At present, there are a series of problems in medical information courses, such as insufficient experimental teaching space, limited experimental funds, and operational restrictions in the experimental process. This paper introduces the virtual simulation experiment mode into the teaching of medical information courses, establishes a new teaching mode and assessment and evaluation system, further improves the teaching quality, and studies the teaching mode suitable for applied medical universities. This paper mainly studies the possibility of applying the virtual simulation experiment mode to medical information class courses, and compares it with the traditional teaching mode and teaching effect to explore a new idea of effectively improving students' innovation and practice ability.

Keywords— Virtual simulation experiment; medical information course; teaching mode.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the rapid development of medicine and information technology, the application of "Internet + medical education" has been widely developed. Artificial intelligence and big data technology have penetrated into all walks of life in the medical field, and medical information technology has become a necessary skill for today's medical students [1], so how to make students better understand the course knowledge and master the course technology has become a decisive factor for the healthy development of medical information courses. At present, there are a series of problems in medical information courses, such as insufficient experimental teaching space, limited experimental funds, and operational limitations in the experimental process, and the shortcomings of the traditional teaching methods of medical information courses are gradually revealed. This paper explores the application of virtual simulation experiment teaching in medical information courses, in order to improve the teaching quality of medical information courses and improve the teaching mode by combining the actual situation and teaching experience of our university.

II. STATUS OF TRADITIONAL TEACHING MODEL

Medical information course is an emerging discipline of cross-fertilization between information science and medicine, and its professional goal is to cultivate professional and practical talents with broad knowledge and strong comprehensive application ability in medical information acquisition, transmission, processing, analysis and storage, etc., and to cultivate practical talents with basic theory and skills of medical and health information technology, who can integrate professional knowledge and skills of medical, computer and information science and other disciplines. The training is to cultivate practical talents with basic theories and skills of health care information technology, who can integrate the professional knowledge and skills of medical, computer and information science. The traditional teaching method mostly adopts LBL (lecture-based learning) teaching method [2], which emphasizes the transmission of classroom knowledge by the teacher, and the teacher teaches theoretical knowledge on the podium, and only occasionally uses questions and random checks on students, which is a more traditional teaching method. Pictures are used to supplement the teaching to help students understand. In simple knowledge points, LBL teaching method can help students understand more intuitively and concisely. However, the more complex and abstract knowledge points are difficult for students to understand and require them to spend more time to understand and know after the class, which may cause students to be tired of the course.

III. VIRTUAL SIMULATION EXPERIMENT TECHNOLOGY APPLICATION ADVANTAGES

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A. Experimental conditions are easy to control

The experimental conditions in medical information course experiments are complex and not easy to control, while in virtual experiments, these conditions parameters can be entered manually by students in the virtual experimental platform, and the experimental conditions are completely controllable [3]. Virtual simulation experiments can effectively solve the problems of time-consuming experiments of medical information resources and equipment science, many internal and external influencing factors, lack of equipment, and can be systematically examined as a whole. In the virtual experiments, students can set any experimental parameters within a reasonable range, and the simulation system can give feedback instantly, which greatly improves the efficiency of experiments [4].

B. Shorten the experimental cycle

In the traditional medical information class experimental teaching, teachers mostly use demonstration experiments, or play experimental teaching videos as a supplement. Students operate according to the teacher's classroom lectures and experimental instructions, and if students make mistakes due to improper operation, it is difficult to complete the experiment in the limited class time, and the experiment can only end in failure, and the grade of the experimental class is low [5]. Experimental videos and experimental instructions are boring, and students have a higher chance of making mistakes in the actual operation. Virtual simulation experiments can be completed to show students the whole experimental process, students can repeat the operation, through the correction of the wrong method, to achieve a high degree of accuracy of the experiment, deepen the students' mastery of knowledge points, stimulate students' enthusiasm and motivation to learn [6].

C. Inspire students' independent thinking skills

Virtual simulation experiments are being accepted by the majority of teachers and students because of their high degree of simulation, accuracy, and safety. Virtual simulation experiments have the function of setting experimental content by themselves, adjusting experimental steps, and regulating various parameters in the experimental process [7]. In this way, we can accurately simulate the data errors and operational errors that exist in the experimental process, improve the ability of students to analyze and solve problems using the knowledge they have learned, avoid the traditional blind operation of students in the process of experimental operations, problems from scratch analysis, time-consuming and laborious

drawbacks, so that students from passive operation, into active learning, teaching and learning, and enhance the innovative thinking ability of students.

IV. MEDICAL INFORMATION CLASS DESIGN

A. Teaching Objectives

The teaching objectives of medical information courses are mainly reflected in three aspects: knowledge, skills, learning attitudes and values. First of all, familiar with the orientation, professional goals and professional development direction of the profession; understand the curriculum of the profession, as well as the correlation between different courses, know the requirements of the relevant practical skills that need to be mastered in the profession, and be clear about the direction of employment development. In the process of professional courses, we strengthen the cultivation of students' hands-on ability and comprehensive ability, stimulate students' creative thinking, and help them plan their studies and careers to expand their professional knowledge.

B. Instructional Implementation Strategies

Medical information courses are mainly taught by lectures (including microlearning and online classroom guide forms), visits, field experiences and exchanges. In the professional course learning phase, students are mainly led to learn professional knowledge through the teaching method of lecture. In the field visit phase, the teaching method of show and tell is used to let students experience the information expertise and the specific application in the field of Chinese medicine in hospitals through field visits. In the hands-on learning phase, students are guided by an inquiry-based interactive teaching method to enhance their understanding and appreciation of the importance of hands-on skills. The lecture and exchange phase, mainly through the teaching form of lecture and exchange, employs teachers from the university and enterprises to explain the content related to the profession and understand how to apply medical information expertise to solve practical problems.

C. Formative Evaluation Program Tables

Formative evaluation, i.e. process evaluation, is mainly aimed at dynamically monitoring students' learning status and urging them to learn. The main purpose of the medical information course is to examine students' familiarity with their professional orientation and goals, to understand the medical information professional curriculum, and to develop professional study plans and future career development plans. Therefore, the following formative assessment scheme was set. For details, please refer to Table 1.

TABLE I. FORMATIVE EVALUATION PROGRAM

Formative evaluation points	Percentage of each rating
Attendance in class	10
Understanding of professional course system	10
Professional study plan and development plan	20

Field visits and new experiences in practice	20
Final Course Paper Final Course Paper	40
Total	100

CONCUSLION

Virtual simulation experimental technology can provide students with a concise and clear teaching environment, through real-time simulation, the original relatively simple theoretical lectures become more in-depth, inspire and guide students to think deeply. Simulation virtual technology is a technology derived from the real, highly imitated real experimental process, is a virtual experiment in a simulated environment, can be intuitive and efficient technical means to obtain indirect experience, but can not fully demonstrate all the possibilities of the actual experimental operation, some of the actual experimental process of unknown factors may cause errors in the real experimental results, while it also can not give students a deep lessons of experimental errors. Therefore, in the process of using simulation virtual technology for teaching, students need to be correctly guided to understand that simulation virtual technology is only an aid and supplement to real experimental teaching, and it cannot completely replace all the operational problems and means that will occur in real experiments. At the same time, it also provides reference and reference for the information construction and discipline reform of pharmaceutical universities.

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